

Research Article

Modeling Relationships between Land Surface Temperature and Selected Vegetation Indices using Geo-Spatial Techniques: A Case Study of Oluwa Forest Reserve, Ondo State

Aigbokhan O. J*, Ekundayo A. A, Essien N. E., Ukoha A. P.

Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria, Department of Environmental Modeling and Biometrics, Remote Sensing and GIS Section.

*Corresponding author: oseyomon255@gmail.com

Abstract

This paper tends to explain the application of Remote Sensing (RS) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) for analysis and monitoring the relationships of land surface temperature (LST) with selected vegetation indices in the area. For mapping purposes, satellite images of Landsat-8 OLI / TIRS images, acquired on the 1st of April 2018 were used. The study was conducted in Oluwa fragmented Forest Reserve, situated in Ondo State of Nigeria. The study was based on Landsat 8 (OLI/TIR) only because the emphasis was not on time series. The temperature values were extracted using Remote Sensing algorithms from thermal infrared (TIR) data (band 10). The calculations of five vegetation indices were also done with their result regressed with the land surface temperature. Therefore, the main objective is to examine the degree of relationship between LST and some selected vegetation indices. The processing and analysis of data was done using ArcGIS and IDRISI software systems. The results revealed that the LST ranged from 24°C to 36°C with a mean of 30°C). From the correlation analysis, RVI has the strongest relationship (-0.6) with the prevailing LST than other vegetation indices. This implies that remote sensing and GIS techniques are reliable and therefore could be employed for large scale temperature mapping and the modeling of vegetation indices.

Keywords: Land surface temperature; vegetation indices; OLI/TIR; and algorithm.

Received: 28/06/18

Accepted: 04/09/18

Introduction

Conventionally, land surface temperature (LST) is usually acquired through direct observation by using a network of local meteorological stations. Though data on weather elements could easily be obtained from these meteorological stations, but are expensive, poorly dispersed and difficult to convert into raster surface using interpolation techniques (Zaharaddeen *et al.*, 2016). LST is the key factor for calculating highest and lowest temperature of a location. Medium spatial resolution data, such as that from the LANDSAT is suitable for land cover or vegetation mapping at regional local scale. LANDSAT 8 carries two sensors, i.e., the Operational Land Imager (OLI) and the Thermal Infrared Sensor (TIRS). OLI collects data at a 30m spatial resolution with eight bands located in the visible and near-infrared and the shortwave infrared regions of the electromagnetic spectrum, and an additional panchromatic band of 15m spatial resolution. TIRS senses the TIR radiance at a spatial resolution of 100m using two bands located in the atmospheric window between 10 and 12 μm (Anandababu *et al.*, 2018). Remote Sensing data are essentially affordable and generally adopted by researchers with spatial reference in meteorology because remote sensing data is available on a regular basis (Karnieli *et al.*, 2010). The land surface temperature is used in many fields, including climate change, hydrological cycle, evapotranspiration, urban climate, vegetation monitoring, environmental studies and others Bobrinskaya (2012). Vegetation indices are mathematical transformations, usually ratios or linear combinations of reflectance measurements in different spectral bands, especially the visible and near-infrared bands. They are widely used in remote sensing practice to obtain information about surface characteristics from multispectral measurements, taking advantage of differences in the reflectance patterns between green vegetation and other surfaces.

Vegetation indices use spectral bands that are sensitive to plants. The red and near-infrared bands are usually used in this method because of their sensitivities in detecting vegetal cover. Out of all the vegetation indices, NDVI is the most widely applied to monitor vegetation change on regional and local scales. NDVI combines two channels (NIR and RED) in a normalized ratio, which makes it possible to differentiate vegetation cover signal from other objects as shown below. The lowest value represents the difference between the red and NIR, and especially indicates that the red value is higher than the NIR signal. A higher value signifies a larger difference between the red and near infrared radiation recorded by the sensor.

This paper tends to explain the application of Remote Sensing (RS) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) for analysis and monitoring the relationships of land surface

temperature (LST) with selected vegetation indices in the area. Therefore, the main objective is to examine the degree of relationship between LST and some selected vegetation indices.

Study Area

The study area is Oluwa Forest Reserve in the South-western part of Nigeria. It lies between latitudes 6°37' and 7°20' North and longitudes 4°27' and 5°05' East. The elevation is approximately between 300 and 600 metres above the sea. Hydrologically, the major rivers and streams in the study area are Owena, Oni, Oluwa, and Ominla. The mean annual rainfall ranges from 1,200mm to 1450mm and temperatures are high throughout the year with a mean of about 27°C with an annual range of about 30°C. The study area falls within the tropical rainforest characterized by multiple canopies and lianas. Some of the most commonly found trees in the area include *Melicia excelsa*, *Azalia bipindensis*, *Antiaris africana*, *Brachystegia nigerica*, *Lophira alata*, *Louoa trichiliodes*, *Terminalia ivorensis*, *Terminalia superba*, *Triplochiton scleroxylon*, etc. However, the natural vegetation of the area with the exception of the areas devoted to forest reserve has now been reduced to secondary regrowth forest thickets and fallow regrowth at different stages of development or replaced by perennial and annual crops (Orimoogunje *et al.*, 2005).

Figure 1: Map of the study area.

Methodology

Data Acquisition

The main sources of data collection were used to obtain primary and secondary data. The most important data in this study were the satellite data. Other data were collected from governmental and nongovernmental organizations and published materials.

The primary data i.e. Landsat 8 OLI/TIR image captured on 1st of April 2018 was downloaded freely from official Earth Explorer USGS distribution website (earthexplorer.usgs.gov). The satellite imagery was referenced to the Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) Projection System. The published research work of different relevant articles was used to provide guidance for this study.

Software

After the collection of data, RS and GIS software were used for the analysis and further processing. These are ERDAS Imagine 2013, IDRISI Selva and ArcGIS 10.3

Geo-spatial Techniques

First, the raw image was radiometrically corrected by converting the DN values to at-sensor radiance. Secondly the image was atmospherically corrected by calculating spectral reflectance with the use of the spectral radiance.

Land Surface Temperature

Land surface temperature (LST) is the main factor used to determine energy exchange and surface radiation (Bobrinskaya, 2012). In recent times, the most widely used methods to retrieve LST is to employ thermal infrared (TIR) -remote sensing data. The following equations were obtained in the Landsat User’s Handbook (NASA, 2015)

$$Radiance = \frac{LMAX - LMIN}{QCALMAX - QCALMIN} \times (QCAL - QCALMIN) + LMIN \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where,

- LMAX = the spectral radiance that is scaled to QCALMAX in W/ (m² * sr * m)
- LMIN = the spectral radiance that is scaled to QCALMIN in W/ (m² * sr * m)
- QCALMIN = the minimum quantized calibrated pixel value (corresponding to LMIN) in DN = 1,
- QCALMAX = the maximum quantized calibrated pixel value (corresponding to LMIN) in 65535 (landsat-8 OLI / TIRS)
- QCAL = DN

The second stage is to convert Atmospheric-Satellite Brightness Temperature to Kelvin. To calculate this, brightness temperature, NDVI, and emissivity were calculated from OLI image, which were then used to compute LST.

$$TB = K2 / \log \{ (K1 / Radiance) + 1 \} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where,

- TB = the effective at-satellite brightness temperature in Kelvin;
- K1 = 666.09 (watts/ (meter²sterμm))
- K2 = 1282.71 (Kelvin) are calibration constants.

Finally, LST is estimated using: $BT / (1 + W * (BT / P) * \ln(e)) \dots \dots \dots (3)$

Where;

- TB = Brightness Temperature
- Wavelength of emitted radiance = (10.6μm)
- e = Land surface emissivity
- Land surface emissivity (e) = $0.004P_v + 0.986 \dots \dots \dots (4)$

Where;

Pv = Proportional vegetation

Pv = (NDVI -NDVImin/NDVImax-NDVImin)

Table 1. The characteristics of satellite data used.

Satellite/Sensor	Date	Path/Roll	Bands	Spectral resolution (μm)	Spatial resolution (m)
Landsat 8 (OLI/TIR)	01 / 04 / 2018	190 / 055	Band 1	0.435-0.451	30
			Band 2	0.452 - 0.512	30
			Band 3	0.533 - 0.590	30
			Band 4	0.636 - 0.673	30
			Band 5	0.851 - 0.879	30
			Band 6	1.566 - 1.651	30
			Band 7	2.107 - 2.294	30
			Band 8	0.503 - 0.676	15
			Band 9	1.363 - 1.384	30
			Band 10	10.60 - 11.19	100
			Band 11	11.50 - 12.51	100

Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)

Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) is used as an indicator of biomass and greenness. The value ranges from +1 to -1. The positive value indicates a vegetated area and a negative value indicates a non-vegetated area. The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) was introduced by Rouse *et al.* (1974) to produce a spectral VI that separates green vegetation from its background soil brightness using Landsat digital data. It is expressed as the difference between the near infrared and red bands normalized by the sum of those bands. The formula is given as equation 5:

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR-RED}{NIR+RED} \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

Transformed Normalized Difference Vegetation index (TNDVI)

Transformed Normalized Difference Vegetation index (TNDVI) is the square root of the NDVI. It has higher coefficient of determination for the same variable and this is the difference between TNDVI and NDVI. The formula of TNDVI has always positive values and the variances of the ratio are proportional to mean values. TNDVI indicates a relation between the amounts of green biomass that is found in a pixel. A constant of 0.5 was added and to approximate the normal distribution, a square root was introduced. Tucker (1979) proposed this formula:

$$TNDVI = \sqrt{NDVI + 0.5} \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

Infrared Percentage Vegetation Index (IPVI)

Crippen (1990) found that the subtraction of the red band in the numerator of the NDVI was irrelevant, and proposed this index as a way of improving calculation speed. IPVI is restricted to values between 0 and 1 (as opposed to -1 to +1 for NDVI), which eliminates the need for storing a sign for the vegetation index values, and eliminates the conceptual strangeness of potentially negative values for vegetation indices.

$$IPVI = \frac{NIR}{NIR+RED} \dots\dots\dots (7)$$

Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (SAVI)

This model was initiated by (Huete, 1988). The index ranges from -1 to +1. Where L is a correction factor which ranges from 0 for very high vegetation cover to 1 for very low vegetation cover. The most typically used value is 0.5 which is for intermediate vegetation cover.

$$SAVI = \frac{NIR-RED}{NIR+RED+L} \times (1 + L) \dots\dots\dots (8)$$

Ratio Vegetation Index (RVI)

This widely calculated vegetation index was first described by Jordan (1969). It is also known as the Simple Ratio (SR) index. A common practice in remote sensing is the use of band ratios to eliminate various albedo effects. Many people use the ratio of near-IR to red to show the vegetation component of a scene; this is the RVI. The denominator (red reflectance) gets smaller and numerator (near-IR reflectance) gets larger as the amount of green vegetation increases. Typical ranges are a little more than 1 for bare soil to more than 20 for dense vegetation

$$RVI = \frac{NIR}{RED} \dots\dots\dots (9)$$

Sampling Procedure

Prior to sampling the data, we determined the number of samples necessary to detect differences in vegetation indices of significance. Using the procedures outlined in Montgomery (1991), we chose 500 sample points to extract values from temperature map and all the vegetation indices we examined. These sample points were generated using ArcGIS 10.3 software. The points were used for all statistical analysis reported in the article. Simple linear regression was used to initiate analyses of individual vegetation indices. For each vegetation index, coefficients of determination (R²) were examined to determine the amount of variability explained by the best fitting models.

Results and Discussion

The independent variable in this analysis is the land surface temperature. This explains why a lot of premium is placed on the spatial distribution of LST of Landsat-8 OLI / TIRS, captured on the 01-04-2018. The LST ranged from 24°C to 36°C with a mean of 30°C. The south-eastern part of the study area exhibits the highest temperature range (30°C to 36°C). This is consequent upon the dominance of non-forest land cover type (figures 2 and 3). Lowest temperature ranges (24 °C to 26 °C) occur in the forested area and water bodies.

Approximately 500 random points were used to extract values from the LST image and the images of the selected vegetation indices. Land surface temperature values and values of the five vegetation indices were acquired to find the strength of the relationship between LST and the selected vegetation indices, using the instrumentality of regression analysis. Looking at the coefficient of determination (R^2) of each of the models (Figures 9 to 13), RVI performed best ($R^2=0.3579$), followed by TNDVI ($R^2 = 0.3478$), NDVI ($R^2 = 0.3402$), SAVI ($R^2= 0.3402$), and IPVI ($R^2= 0.3402$). From the correlation analysis (Table 2), RVI has stronger relationship (-0.6) with the prevailing LST than other vegetation indices. The rest of the indices have almost the same degree of relationship with LST. This invariably means that the effect of vegetation cover on LST could better be described or explained using RVI. From the table, the closest index to RVI in terms of relationship is NDVI (0.9964) therefore, NDVI could be used in place of RVI to determine LST dynamics resulting from vegetation cover changes.

Figure2: Land Cover map of the study area as at 2018.

Figure 3: Map of the study area showing the Land Surface Temperature

Figure 4: Map of the study area showing the Normalized Ratio Vegetation Index (RVI)

Figure 5: Map of the study area showing the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)

Figure 6: Map of the study area showing the Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (SAVI)

Figure 7: Map of the study area showing the Infrared Percentage Vegetation Index (IPVI)

Figure 8: Map of the study area showing the Transformed Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (TNDVI)

Figure 9: Relationship between land surface temperature (LST) and the Ratio Vegetation Index (RVI).

Figure 10: Relationship between land surface temperature (LST) and Infrared Percentage Vegetation Index (IPVI)

Figure 11: Relationship between land surface temperature (LST) and Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (SAVI)

Figure 12: Relationship between land surface temperature (LST) and the Transformed Normalized Difference Vegetation index (TNDVI)

Figure 13: Relationship between land surface temperature (LST) and the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)

Table 2: Correlation between land surface temperature and five selected vegetation indices

	<i>LST</i>	<i>NDVI</i>	<i>TNDVI</i>	<i>SAVI</i>	<i>IPVI</i>	<i>RVI</i>
<i>LST</i>	1	0.99454-	0.99537-	-0.98661	-0.9964	0.593632
<i>NDVI</i>	-0.5783	1	0.99801	0.995148	0.997962	-0.57748
<i>TNDVI</i>	-0.57817	0.989899	1	0.987979	0.996713	-0.57952
<i>SAVI</i>	-0.57952	0.996713	0.987979	1	0.989899	-0.57817
<i>IPVI</i>	-0.57748	0.997962	0.995148	0.99801	1	-0.5783
<i>RVI</i>	0.593632	-0.9964	-0.98661	0.99537-	0.99454-	1

Conclusion

This study has revealed that the extraction of land surface temperature values using the instrumentality of Remote Sensing and GIS, has added new dimensions to environment-related researches. Therefore, these techniques are effective for the assessment of the major variables like vegetation indices and land surface temperature). From the correlation analysis, RVI has the strongest relationship (-0.6) with the prevailing LST than other vegetation indices. This implies that remote sensing and GIS techniques are reliable and therefore could be employed for large scale temperature mapping and the modeling of vegetation indices.

References

- Anandababu, B M Purushothaman, Babu S. Suresh (2018). Estimation of and Surface Temperature using LANDSAT 8 Data. *International Journal of Advance Research, Ideas and Innovations in Technology*, 4 (2): 177-186.
- Bobrinskaya M (2012). Remote Sensing for Analysis of relationships between Land Cover and Land Surface Temperature in Ten Megacities. Masters of Science Thesis in Geoinformatics, TRITA-GIT EX 12-008, School of Architecture and the Built Environment, Royal Institute of Technology (KTH), Stockholm, Sweden 2012.
- Crippen, R. E. (1990). Calculating the vegetation index faster. *Remote Sensing of Environment* 34 (1): 71-73.
- Huete, A. R. (1988). A soil-adjusted vegetation index (SAVI). *Remote Sens. Environ.* 25 (3), 295-309.
- Jordan, C. F. (1969), Derivation of leaf-area index from quality of light on the forest floor. *Ecology* 50:663-666.
- Karnieli A, Agam N, Pinker RT, Anderson M, Imhoff ML, Gutman GG (2010). Use of NDVI and land surface temperature for drought assessment: Merits and limitations. *Journal of Climate* 2010; 23: 618-633. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1175/2009JCLI2900.1>
- Montgomery D. C. (1991). Design and Analysis of Experiment. 3rd Edition, John Wiley.
- NASA (2015). Landsat 8 Science Data Users Handbook (United States). <http://landsat.usgs.gov/landsat8.php>

Orimoogunje, O.O.I., Ekanade, O., and Adesina, F.A. (2009). Land use changes and forest reserve management in a changing environment: South-western Nigeria experience. *Journal of Geography and Regional Planning*, 2 (11), pp. 283 - 290.

Rouse, J. W., Haas, R. H., Schell, J. A., Deering, D. W., and Harlan, J. C. (1974), Monitoring the vernal advancement and retrogradation (green wave effect) of natural vegetation, NASA/GSFC Type III Final Report, Greenbelt, MD.

Tucker, C. J. (1979), Red and photographic infrared linear combinations for monitoring vegetation. *Remote Sens. Environ.* 8:127-150.

Zaharaddeen, I, Baba, I.I. and Zachariah, A. (2016) Estimation of Land Surface Temperature of Kaduna Metropolis, Nigeria Using Landsat Images. *Science World Journal*, 11, 36-42. 9.